

- ⁵ Dhare, *opt cited* .
- ⁶ R.E. *Enthoven*, The Tribes and Castes of Bombay. Vol. II, Bombay, 1922, p.
- ⁷ V.Rangacharya., A Topographical list of the inscriptions of Madras Presidency, Asian Educational Services, , New Delhi, 1986, Vol-II.
- ⁸ Ibid.
- ⁹ Ibid.
- ¹⁰ Crooke, William, The Cult of Mother Goddesses in India, Folklore, XXX, p. 300.
- ¹¹ F. J. *Richards*, 'Some Dravidian Affinities and their Sequel', Quarterly Journal of Mythic Society
- ¹² Madhav Milind, Sri Ekaveera Mahatmya (A hymn in Marathi), Jayesh Prakashan, Bombay, 1976. P.8
- ¹³ Dhare., *Opt cited* .
- ¹⁴ Hardy, friedhelm., The Religious Culture of India: Power, Love and Wisdom. Oxford University Press 2005, p. 340.
- ¹⁵ M.K.Dhavalikar., Sakambhari-The Headless Goddess., Abhori:R.G.Bhandarkar 150th Birth Anniversary Volume
- ¹⁶ Ibid.
- ¹⁷ Henry Whitehead, The Religious life of India- The Village Gods of South India, Oxford University press, 1916
- ¹⁸ J. Sujana Mallika., A Socio-Cultural Study of Basavi system in Kurnool District of Andhra Pradesh., unpublished theisis submitted to S.V.University, Tirupati.p.p 56-59
- ¹⁹ P.c.Bagchi (Ed.)Kaulagnananirnaya, Calcutta Sanskrit Series, PP vi-vii.
- ²⁰ Ibid.
- ²¹ Sanjeeva Rao.Rasasiddhas of Alampur, Bulletin India, Institute of History of Medicine, vol.XIII. pp38-44
- ²² Ziegenbalg, Bartholomaeus.; Jeyaraj, Daniel Genealogy of the South Indian Deities : An English Translation of Bartholomaeus Ziegenbalg's Original German Manuscript With a Textual Analysis and Glossary.Taylor & Francis Routledge,2005.
- ²³ Ibid.

HOARD COINS OF REVOOR VILLAGE, NALGONDA DISTRICT, 1978

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The Vishnukundina dynasty was an Indian imperial power controlling the Deccan, Odisha and parts of South India during the 5th and 6th centuries, carving land out from the Vakataka Empire. It played an important role in the history of the Deccan during the 5th and 6th centuries. During the reign of Madhava Varma the Great, they became independent and conquered coastal Andhra from the Salankayanas and might have shifted their capital to a place in the Coastal Andhra. The Vishnukundin reign came to an end with the conquest of the eastern Deccan by the Chalukya Pulakeshin II. Pulakeshin appointed his brother Kubja Vishnuvardhana as Viceroy to rule over the conquered lands. Eventually Vishnuvardhana declared his independence and started the Eastern Chalukya dynasty.

ISSUERS OF THE COIN TYPES

The Vishnukundins minted coins using a unique method: First, the circular coin flan was produced by the casting process and later, the designs and symbols were die- struck on the coin. Unlike the predecessor - Ikshvakus, the Vishnukundins produced coins in copper and potin, not in lead. The designs and motifs on the coins of Vishnukundins shows that Satavahanas coinage might have inspired them. The earliest of Vishnukundin coins feature the humped bull. The majority of the Vishnukundin coins, however, portray a lion standing right with a twisted and uplifted tail and an open mouth. The lion was the dynastic emblem of the Vishnukundins. Sixteen types of coins of the Vishnukundin rulers have been found by

archaeologists in entire Deccan. But, only Lion type coins available in Andhra Hoards.

The reverse of the Vishnukundin coins mostly carried sankha (shell) between two lamps. Varieties of the coin reverses carried the pot (vase) with surmounted flames. The pot may represent a fire altar or a fire pot from which, as per legend, the remote ancestors of the Vishnukundins emerged. In sanskrit, it is referred as Poorna Kumbha - the pot overflowing with flowers and coins. The Poorna Kumbha signifies auspiciousness, prosperity and joy. Other religious motifs such as swastika, sun, crescent, moon, conch and wheel could be seen on their coins.

Vishnukundins coins were made from ternary alloy consisting of copper, iron and tin, containing about 22% iron, 75.4% copper, 3% tin. As for the metal of these coins, it is interesting to note that Vishnukundins were the first to have used iron as a core material for their coins, which were coated with copper alloy at the top.

Vishnukundin coins found in Keesara Village, Rangareddy District (Present Telangana state), Tangudupalli, Vijayanagaramu District, Korukonda, East Godavari District Talukunta Village, Karimnagar District (Present Telangana state) and other places. These coins are preserved in AP State Archaeology and Museums, Hyderabad. Now, we selected one Hoard of coins from Revoor village, Nalgonda District for this present research paper.

There are 262 coins discovered from Revoor village and Huzur Nagar taluk of Nalgonda District, Andhra Pradesh (Present Telangana state) in 1978. Now, 258 coins are preserved in Andhra Pradesh State Museum and Archaeology and remaining 4 coins preserved in various district museums of Andhra Pradesh. These are uninscribed coins of various rulers. Copper or alloyed metal used for making coins.

Obverse: Lion facing left, mouth open, left forepaw raised. Double 'ya' symbol before the mouth and tail lifted up. (S.No.2)

Reverse: Vase in pellet on two slender legs with two curved lines and a lamp stand on either side all in a rayed circle. Consisting of a dvitala vimana with a circular sikhara topped by a single kalasa stupa.

Obverse: Lion facing left, mouth open, left forepaw raised. Double 'ya' symbol before the mouth and crescent above the animal with dotted circular border and tail lifted up. (S.No.174)

Reverse: Vase in one pellet on two slender legs with two curved lines and a lamp stand on either side all in a rayed circle, consisting of a dvitala vimana with a circular sikhara topped by a single kalasa stupa.

Obverse: This coin is partially visible (S.No. 250). Lion facing left, mouth open, left forepaw raised and remaining features are same as above coin.

Reverse: Vase in one pellet on two slender legs with two curved lines and a lamp stand on either side all in a rayed circle, consisting of a dvitala vimana with a circular sikhara.

Most of the coins have same features but not clear visible. Some coins (S.No. 24, 38, 84, 97, 120, 121, 137, 149, 151, 155, 198, 219, 227, 235, 236, 244) are partially broken. This data and analysis helped for the study of the coins and also origin and evolution of the coin system of the Vishnukundins. All the coins in the collection of the museums are without any legend and hence they cannot be ascribed to any individual rulers of this dynasty.

Results

The results are listed in table and histograms

S.No.	SIZE (CMs)	WEIGHT (GMs)			
			38.	2.02	8.34
			39.	2.02	9.45
			40.	2.02	11
			41.	2.03	10.25
1.	2.01	9.25	42.	2	7.46
2.	2.15	11.45	43.	2.04	9.58
3.	2.01	11.45	44.	2.01	10.61
4.	2.02	9.3	45.	2.04	10.95
5.	2	7	46.	2.03	10.52
6.	2.2	9.99	47.	2.03	10.21
7.	2.25	10.67	48.	2.01	9.79
8.	2.25	9.8	49.	2.04	9.91
9.	2.02	9.52	50.	2.05	10.23
10.	2.01	8.15	51.	2.03	10.48
11.	2.25	8.96	52.	2.04	11.84
12.	2.15	8.49	53.	2.05	8.85
13.	2	10.41	54.	2.02	11.01
14.	2.02	9.35	55.	2.02	8.89
15.	2.15	9.3	56.	2.04	9.93
16.	2.01	12.36	57.	2	7.44
17.	2.02	9	58.	2.04	10.21
18.	2.15	9.18	59.	2.05	8.95
19.	2.05	9.59	60.	2.03	8.98
20.	2.25	9.61	61.	2.02	9.94
21.	2.15	11.38	62.	2.05	11.18
22.	2.03	10.1	63.	2.01	10.77
23.	2	8.45	64.	2.01	9.34
24.	2.02	9.78	65.	2.04	10.38
25.	2.02	10.4	66.	2.02	8.04
26.	2.03	8.89	67.	2.02	10.39
27.	2	9.14	68.	2.02	10.04
28.	2.01	10.65	69.	2.01	7.7
29.	2.03	11.22	70.	2.07	10.03
30.	2.04	11.51	71.	2.01	8.09
31.	2.03	10.52	72.	2.05	10.58
32.	2.01	9.8	73.	2.04	8.5
33.	2.05	9.67	74.	2.02	10.36
34.	2.15	8.81	75.	2.03	7.78
35.	2	7.92	76.	2.02	9.79
36.	2.03	9.75	77.	2.03	9.88
37.	2.03	10.63			

78.	2.04	9.43	118.	2.03	9.91
79.	2.05	10.29	119.	2.03	10.42
80.	2.01	9.18	120.	2.01	7.17
81.	2.03	8.62	121.	2.02	7.4
82.	2.02	11.37	122.	2.05	10.08
83.	2.01	10.21	123.	2.02	8.31
84.	2.03	11.85	124.	2.03	9.95
85.	2.04	10.82	125.	2.04	10.35
86.	2.02	9.82	126.	2.01	9.28
87.	2.04	9.63	127.	2.01	9.79
88.	2	7.73	128.	2.03	10.5
89.	2.06	9.51	129.	2.04	10.58
90.	2.03	10.2	130.	2.03	11.55
91.	2.04	11.62	131.	2.01	9.83
92.	2.02	9.53	132.	2.03	9.85
93.	2.03	11.4	133.	2.04	10.56
94.	2	10.48	134.	2.03	10.44
95.	1.09	9.08	135.	2.01	10.36
96.	2.02	10.53	136.	2.03	10.46
97.	2.02	10.26	137.	2.04	11.15
98.	2.02	8.95	138.	2.03	8.83
99.	2.02	10.43	139.	2.03	10.43
100.	2.04	8.5	140.	2.03	9.9
101.	2.02	9.47	141.	2.01	8.5
102.	2.02	10.75	142.	2.01	8.25
103.	2.02	9.76	143.	2.03	11.2
104.	2.03	9.16	144.	2	8.39
105.	2.04	10.1	145.	2.01	3.87
106.	2.04	11.01	146.	2.05	8.95
107.	2.03	10.63	147.	2.03	8.95
108.	2.02	10.42	148.	2.03	9.45
109.	2.02	9.64	149.	2.02	6.68
110.	2.02	9.25	150.	2.01	9.17
111.	2.05	13	151.	-	6.07
112.	2.02	9.35	152.	2.02	8.55
113.	2.03	10.87	153.	2.03	9.03
114.	2.02	9.05	154.	2.02	6.32
115.	2.03	10.59	155.	1.09	2.1
116.	2.02	9.69	156.	2.01	7.88
117.	2.02	9.99	157.	2.01	9.29

158.	2.02	8.41	198.	2.1	7.8
159.	2.03	9.92	199.	2.02	9.67
160.	2.04	9.5	200.	2.01	11.17
161.	2.03	9.52	201.	2.04	10.79
162.	2.02	10.11	202.	2.03	9.17
163.	2.03	7.69	203.	2.03	10.41
164.	2.03	10.2	204.	2.01	9.43
165.	2.04	11.72	205.	2.02	9.08
166.	2.02	10.36	206.	2.03	9.95
167.	2.02	7.83	207.	1.09	7.1
168.	2.01	7.04	208.	2.03	8.59
169.	2	2.92	209.	2.03	8.46
170.	2.05	11	210.	2.02	8.82
171.	1.09	9.91	211.	2.01	9.12
172.	2.02	8.68	212.	2.02	9.75
173.	2.01	9.87	213.	2.03	9.91
174.	2.03	9.97	214.	2.02	10.8
175.	2.04	9.89	215.	2.02	8.89
176.	2.01	5.5	216.	2.02	9.87
177.	2.04	9.92	217.	2.03	10.49
178.	2.03	9.84	218.	2.04	9.71
179.	2.03	9.29	219.	-	8.61
180.	2.01	9.35	220.	2.04	8.96
181.	2.05	9.65	221.	2.03	11.75
182.	2.01	8.7	222.	2.03	9.23
183.	2.01	11.94	223.	2.01	10.8
184.	2.04	12.42	224.	2.02	7.09
185.	2.03	9.01	225.	2.01	9.75
186.	2	7.94	226.	2.02	11.75
187.	2.02	8.62	227.	2.02	9.31
188.	2.03	10.25	228.	2.01	10.01
189.	2.04	10.11	229.	2	8.42
190.	2	6.29	230.	2.03	8.46
191.	2.03	9.89	231.	2.02	8.52
192.	2.01	9.36	232.	2.01	11.15
193.	2.03	10.36	233.	2.03	10.45
194.	2.04	10.37	234.	2.02	8.45
195.	2.01	9.5	235.	2.03	10.13
196.	2.03	9.42	236.	2.02	10.81
197.	2.06	9.26	237.	2.01	10.07

238.	2	7.14
239.	2	8.14
240.	2.03	11.02
241.	2.04	10.08
242.	2.02	9.34
243.	2.03	11.27
244.	-	3.54
245.	1.06	2.12
246.	2.01	8.91
247.	2.05	9.8
248.	2.04	11.53
249.	2.05	8.72
250.	2.03	10.57
251.	2.03	10.45
252.	2.03	10.1
253.	2.02	10.78
254.	2.01	9.25
255.	2.05	8.79
256.	2.03	12.46
257.	2.01	9.92
258.	2.02	8.76

Discussion

The weights of copper coins ranged between 2.1-13 grams. It is obvious that the coins of various denominations were issued. The mean weight of copper coins was 9.53 grams.

Conclusion:

These coins have useful to know the political boundaries of the Vishnukundin rulers. A cultural study of coins from the points of view of religious symbols, iconography, and technological developments would be highly rewarding exercise. The vase or purnakumba one of the eight auspicious symbols is found on the Vishnukundin coins. A large number of animals have been depicted on these coins. A typological classification of lion or elephant or other animals would add to our knowledge of the contemporary times. Lion type coins available in Andhra.

References

1. M.Rama Rao, Vishnukundin Coins in the Andhra Pradesh Government Museum, Hyderabad, 1963.
2. Devendra Handa, Coins and Temples, Numismatic Evidence on the Evolution of Temple Architecture, 2007
3. S.Sankaranarayanan, The Vishnukundins and their times, 1977.
4. A.V. Narasimha Murthy & D. Raja Reddy, Silver, Copper and Other Metal Coins in the Srivari Hundi of Lord Sri Venkateswara, TTD, Tirupathi, 2013.

